

Appendix B: Stellar velocity maps

In this section, we present the stacked and spatially-resolved stellar kinematics map for all the galaxies in the LEWIS sample.

Fig. 1: Stacked (1D) and spatially-resolved (2D) stellar kinematics of UDG3. Top left panel: MUSE reconstructed image of UDG1. The red ellipse represents the elliptical region used to extract the stacked spectrum within $1R_{\text{eff}}$, while the grey circles are the masked image regions. The top label reports the values of the semi-major axis (a), position angle (PA) and ellipticity (ϵ) of the ellipse. Top right panel: MUSE $1R_{\text{eff}}$ stacked spectrum (black solid line) for UDG1. The bottom label reports the fit type: constrained fit (C), intermediate-quality fit (I), and unconstrained fit (U). The main absorption features are marked with magenta lines and labels. The red solid line represents the best-fitting spectrum obtained with pPXF. Green points are the residuals between the observed and its best-fitting spectrum. The grey areas are the masked spectral regions excluded from the fit. Residual points excluded from the fit are marked in blue. Bottom left panel: Voronoi binned map of the S/N. Bottom middle panel: Stellar velocity map subtracted from systemic velocity V_{sys} . The top label reports the type of rotation: rotation along the major photometric axis (R), rotation along an intermediate axis (IR), no rotation (NR). The blue and red lines mark the photometric major and minor axes of the galaxy, respectively. Bottom right panel: Velocity profiles extracted along the major (top) and minor (bottom) axes and subtracted from V_{sys} .

Fig. 2: Same as Figure 1, but for UDG4.

Fig. 3: Same as Figure 1, but for UDG7.

Fig. 4: Same as Figure 1, but for UDG8.

Fig. 5: Same as Figure 1, but for UDG9.

Fig. 6: Same as Figure 1, but for UDG10.

Fig. 7: Same as Figure 1, but for UDG11.

Fig. 8: Same as Figure 1, but for UDG12.

Fig. 9: Same as Figure 1, but for UDG20.

Fig. 10: Same as Figure 1, but for UDG21.

Fig. 11: Same as Figure 1, but for UDG23.

Fig. 12: Same as Figure 1, but for LSB1.

Fig. 13: Same as Figure 1, but for LSB4.

Fig. 14: Same as Figure 1, but for LSB5.

Fig. 15: Same as Figure 1, but for LSB6.

Fig. 16: Same as Figure 1, but for LSB7.

Fig. 17: Same as Figure 1, but for LSB8.

Appendix C: Stellar velocity and velocity dispersion maps

In this section, we present the V_{LOS} and σ_{LOS} maps for a sub-set of galaxies in the LEWIS sample. To ensure an unbiased measure for σ_{LOS} , the Voronoi binning threshold was set to $S/N \geq 15$.

Fig. 18: Stellar V_{LOS} and σ_{LOS} maps for UDG1. Left panel: Voronoi binned map of the S/N with threshold $S/N = 15$. Central panel: stellar V_{LOS} map subtracted from systemic velocity V_{sys} . Right panel: stellar σ_{LOS} map. The black ellipse represents the elliptical region used to extract the V_{rms} with semi-major axis $a = R_{\text{eff}}$.

Fig. 19: Same as Figure 18, but for UDG8.

Fig. 20: Same as Figure 18, but for LSB6.

Fig. 21: Same as Figure 18, but for LSB7.

Fig. 22: Same as Figure 18, but for LSB8.